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**A European comparative study of circular bioeconomy governance strategies
and good governance practices for supporting local operators and innovation
developers in the circular bioeconomy.**

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The circular bioeconomy is a new model for the industry and the economy, that involves using renewable biological resources sustainably to produce food, energy and industrial goods. It also exploits the untapped potential of biological waste, residual materials and wastewater following a cascading use. Over a decade ago, the European Bioeconomy Strategy was launched as the main governance framework to inspire the deployment of policies in the Member States. Since then, the steady progress to adopt strategic frameworks and good governance practices at the national and regional levels may have been accelerated by the European Green Deal (2019). Thus, a plethora of regional authorities in Europe currently pursue strategies to promote and expand their bioeconomies. As of November 2021, 194 regions in EU-27 had a strategic framework for bioeconomy in place or were in the process of doing so. That demonstrates the increasing recognition of the circular (bio)economy in the policy agendas. Due to its cross-sectoral nature, the political support to the bioeconomy currently spans from being set as a multi-sectoral governance model, to be embedded in circular economy roadmaps or other policies (S3, industry-, agriculture-, or environment-related).

This conference paper presents an overview of regional circular bioeconomy governance strategies and models in the EU-27. The literature review investigates potential assessment methods and evidence on the effectiveness and robustness of existing governance schemes in the EU. From the collection of a sample of circular bioeconomy governance case studies, a typology of regional bioeconomy governance models, along ten dimensions is created. This taxonomy distinguishes four bio-based transformation paths and two main governance functions, political support measures (enabling governance) and regulatory tools (constraining governance) with which regions can confront these challenges, to distinguish between the two fundamental political challenges in setting up an effective governance framework for a sustainable bioeconomy. Based solely on the three enabling governance mechanisms and the five constraining governance mechanisms identified, over 15 types of circular bioeconomy governance could be distinguished. Guided by the aforementioned framework, a qualitative content analysis of 20 circular bioeconomy governance strategies was conducted to provide answers to the topic of how well the individual regional bioeconomy strategies are designed to ensure the sustainable rise of bioeconomy in the regions. The analysis of the 20 regional circular bioeconomy governance models selected indicates

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that bio-based research and development strategies are present within 60% of the regional bioeconomy models selected, whereas enhancing the competitiveness of bio-based products through subsidies is present in 40% of the governance models and implementing awareness-raising campaigns to increase societal participation in bio-based transformation, including more responsible and sustainable consumption is present in 25% of the governance models. This research shows how many regions have set the goal of developing and expanding their bioeconomies, how local governments are providing comprehensive political support to their bioeconomies to achieve these goals, how regions address the enabling governance challenge and what is the level of the attention that the political management of conflicting goals has reached.

This research also investigated the different types of good governance practices which are developed from the aforementioned bioeconomy governance models. These good governance practices represent different supporting mechanisms or enablers of bioeconomy development. The collection of good governance practices was based on an expanded criteria for defining “good practice” which focuses on validation and uptake, transferability and replicability, and potential to deliverable positive environmental, economic and societal benefits for the regions. 75 practices were collected from across Europe covering a range of different instruments categorized as fiscal and financial instruments (24), regulatory instruments (7), information and advisory instruments (15), networking, collaboration, and joint planning instruments (20), voluntary instruments (3) and other instruments (6). The practices were collected from different territorial contexts, including urban, rural, peri-urban, coastal and uplands. In order to better define the practices and support their uptake and integration at the regional level, the typology developed above has also been applied to the inventory of good practices. From the analysis, the main transformation paths within the practices are linked to fossil fuel substitutions and less emphasis was given on paths regarding boosting primary sector productivity and achieving value creation and addition from biomass. A good balance of enabling government function options (1. awareness raisings to increase societal uptake, 2. investment in R&D, 3. subsidies for bio-based products) was seen within the practices. The presence of constraining government (i.e., safeguarding function of government) is less evident within the practices, and there was a lack of information about potential negative impacts of practices, which, considering the recent emphasis on the requirement for the bioeconomy to operate within the ecological boundaries of the planet, should be an important factor to consider. There was a notable lack of practices which identified as penta-helix, which, given the need for significant capital deployment to scale the bioeconomy is something that will be required. Information and support measures as well as Economic measures (price, taxation or subsidies) were the main driver measures for practices, with most practices identifying as either fully public, or public private, measures indicating that the government still plays a vital role as a driver of bioeconomy implementation in Europe’s regions.

Key words: circular economy; bioeconomy; innovation; sustainability; governance